

Impact of Menopause on Glycemic Indices, Inflammatory Markers, and Total Cholesterol Levels in Women Residing in Onitsha, Anambra State

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Abstract

Menopause is associated with metabolic and cardiovascular changes, yet its impact on glycemic control, inflammation, and lipid profile remains underexplored in Nigerian women. This study assessed the influence of menopause on glycemic indices, inflammatory markers, and total cholesterol levels among women in Onitsha, Anambra State. A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted on premenopausal and postmenopausal women. Anthropometric parameters, blood pressure, fasting plasma glucose (FPG), glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), homeostatic model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR), inflammatory markers [C-reactive protein (CRP), rheumatoid factor (RF), interleukin-6 (IL-6)], and total cholesterol were analyzed. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Postmenopausal women exhibited significantly higher BMI, waist-to-hip ratio, and blood pressure compared to premenopausal controls ($p < 0.05$). FPG, HbA1c, and HOMA-IR were significantly elevated in the postmenopausal group ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, CRP, RF, and IL-6 levels were markedly increased, indicating heightened systemic inflammation. Total cholesterol levels were also significantly higher in postmenopausal women ($p < 0.05$). Regression analysis revealed strong associations between menopause and CRP (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.733$, $\beta = 0.859$, $p = 0.000$) and IL-6 (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.535$, $\beta = 0.738$, $p = 0.000$), suggesting a pronounced inflammatory response. Menopause is significantly associated with impaired glycemic control, increased inflammation, and elevated cholesterol levels, predisposing women to metabolic and cardiovascular risks. These findings highlight the need for targeted interventions to mitigate menopause-related health complications.

Keywords: Menopause, Glycemic Indices, Inflammatory Markers, Total Cholesterol, Cardiovascular Risk, Onitsha.

Introduction

Menopause is a natural biological transition in a woman's life, marked by the cessation of ovarian function and a decline in estrogen levels. This hormonal shift is associated with various metabolic and physiological changes, including alterations in glucose metabolism, lipid profile, and inflammatory responses.^{1,2} Studies have shown that postmenopausal women are at a higher risk of developing insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, and chronic inflammation, which are key contributors to cardiovascular diseases and metabolic disorders.^{3,4}

Glycemic indices, such as fasting blood sugar (FBS) and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), are critical markers for assessing glucose regulation and insulin sensitivity. Postmenopausal hormonal changes may lead to impaired glucose metabolism, increasing the risk of type 2 diabetes.^{5,6} Similarly, inflammatory markers like C-reactive protein (CRP) and interleukin-6 (IL-6) are often elevated in postmenopausal women, reflecting an increased state of systemic inflammation, which has been linked to cardiovascular complications.⁷ Furthermore, menopause has been associated with unfavorable changes in lipid profiles, particularly increased total cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, further predisposing women to atherosclerosis and cardiovascular diseases.⁸

While numerous studies have explored the effects of menopause on these health parameters in diverse populations, regionally specific data, particularly from sub-Saharan African regions like Onitsha, Anambra State, Nigeria, remain limited. This is significant as regional variations in lifestyle, dietary habits, and genetic predispositions can influence the manifestation of menopausal effects. This study aims to evaluate the impact of menopause on glycemic indices, inflammatory markers, and total cholesterol levels among women residing in Onitsha, Anambra State. By comparing premenopausal and postmenopausal women, the findings of this study will contribute to a better understanding of the metabolic and inflammatory alterations associated with menopause, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to improve the health and well-being of aging women.

Materials and Methodology

This cross-sectional comparative study was designed to evaluate the impact of menopause on glycemic indices, lipid profiles, and inflammatory markers among women residing in Onitsha, Anambra State. The study population comprised women aged 30 to 65 years, categorized into two distinct groups: premenopausal women (30-45 years) with regular menstrual cycles, serving as the control group, and postmenopausal women (46-65 years) defined by the absence of menstruation for at least 12 consecutive months.

Participants were recruited from hospitals, community health centers, and residential areas in Onitsha using a stratified random sampling method. Inclusion criteria mandated that participants be within the specified age range, residents of Onitsha, and willing to provide informed consent. Exclusion criteria encompassed women with a history of diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, those receiving hormone replacement therapy (HRT), lipid-lowering drugs, or anti-inflammatory medications, as well as pregnant and lactating women.

The sample size was determined using Cochran's formula to ensure adequate statistical power for comparing metabolic parameters between premenopausal and postmenopausal groups. Ethical approval was obtained from the University Onitsha Research Ethics Committee, and written informed consent was secured from all participants prior to data collection. Strict confidentiality of participant information was maintained throughout the study.

Anthropometric measurements, including body mass index (BMI) and waist-to-hip ratio (WHR), were recorded for each participant. BMI was calculated using the standard formula (weight in kilograms divided by the square of height in meters, kg/m^2), and WHR was determined using a non-stretchable measuring tape.

For biochemical analysis, a 5 mL fasting venous blood sample was collected from each participant under aseptic conditions. Blood samples were processed and analyzed for glycemic indices, lipid profiles, and inflammatory markers. Fasting blood glucose (FBG) was measured using the glucose oxidase method, and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) was assessed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). total cholesterol (TC) was determined using enzymatic colorimetric assays. Serum C-reactive protein (sCRP), a sensitive inflammatory biomarker, and rheumatoid factor (RF), a marker of autoimmune activity, were measured using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

The collected data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation (SD), were used to summarize the variables. Comparative analyses between premenopausal and postmenopausal groups were conducted using independent t-tests. Simple linear regression analysis was employed to determine the independent effects of menopause on glycemic indices, lipid profiles, sCRP, and RF levels. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULT

Postmenopausal women demonstrated significantly higher body mass index (BMI), waist-to-hip ratio (WHR), and blood pressure compared to premenopausal controls ($p < 0.05$), as presented in Table 1.

Additionally, an assessment of glycemic indices revealed a significant increase in fasting plasma glucose (FPG), glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), and homeostatic model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR) among postmenopausal women compared to their premenopausal counterparts ($p < 0.05$), as shown in Table 2.

Similarly, inflammatory markers, including C-reactive protein (CRP), rheumatoid factor (RF), and interleukin-6 (IL-6), were significantly elevated in postmenopausal women ($p < 0.05$), indicating a heightened inflammatory state as shown in table 3. Furthermore, as illustrated in Table 3, total cholesterol levels were significantly higher in the postmenopausal group ($p < 0.05$), suggesting an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases.

Overall, as indicated in table 4, menopause was significantly associated with increased glycemic indices (FPG, HbA1c, HOMA-IR), inflammatory markers (CRP, RF, IL-6), blood pressure (SBP, DBP), and total cholesterol levels. The strongest associations were observed with CRP (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.733$, $\beta = 0.859$, $p = 0.000$) and IL-6 (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.535$, $\beta = 0.738$, $p = 0.000$), indicating that menopause is a major contributor to systemic inflammation. These findings underscore the metabolic and cardiovascular alterations linked to menopause.

Table 1: Comparison of Anthropometric Measurements Between Premenopausal and Postmenopausal Women in Onitsha

Parameter	Pre-Menopause (Control) Mean \pm SD	Menopause Mean \pm SD	P-Value
AGE (years)	39 \pm 2	56 \pm 4.5	0.000*
BMI (kg/m ²)	29.8 \pm 3.3	32 \pm 3.3	0.007*
WHR	0.83 \pm .07	0.97 \pm 0.07	0.000*
SBP (mm/Hg)	136 \pm 12.8	147 \pm 13.7	0.010*
DBP (mm/Hg)	88.8 \pm 6.7	98 \pm 7.8	0.000*

*Significant, $p < 0.05$ significant level

BMI = Body mass index, SBP= Systolic blood pressure, DBP= Diastolic blood pressure. WHR = waist to Hip ratio, W/Height= Weight to height ratio

Table 2 Comparison of Glycemic Indices Between Premenopausal and Postmenopausal Women in Onitsha

Parameter	Pre-Menopause (Control) Mean \pm SD	Menopause Mean \pm SD	P-Value
FPG (mmol/L)	5.2 \pm 0.74	5.8 \pm 0.71	0.000*
INSULIN (μ IU/ml)	11.4 \pm 4.8	16 \pm 6.7	0.009*
HOMA-IR	2.66 \pm 1.1	4.2 \pm 1.9	0.001*
HBA1C (%)	3.6 \pm 1.2	5.6 \pm 1.4	0.000*

*Significant, $p < 0.05$ significant level FPG= Fasting plasma Glucose, HOMA-IR Homeostatic Model Assessment-Insulin Resistance, HBA1C Glycated Hemoglobin

Table 3 Comparison of Inflammatory Markers and Total Cholesterol Between Premenopausal and Postmenopausal Women in Onitsha

Parameter	Pre-Menopause (Control) Mean \pm SD	Menopause Mean \pm SD	P-Value
sCRP (mg/L)	9.1 \pm 1.6	41 \pm 13	0.000*
IL-6 (pg/ml)	9.3 \pm 3.0	29 \pm 12.5	0.000*
RF (IU/ml)	11.3 \pm 2.7	16 \pm 6.3	0.001*
TCHOL (mmol/L)	5.5 \pm 0.83	6.3 \pm 0.77	0.001*

*Significant, $p < 0.05$ significant level TCHOL-C, Total cholesterol, RF= Rheumatoid Factor, IL-6= Interleukin 6, CRP = C-Reactive Protein

Table 4 Association of Menopause with glycemic indices, inflammatory markers, and Total cholesterol

Parameter	Adjusted R ²	Standard Coefficient (Beta)	P-Value
WHR	0.504	0.717	0.000*
SBP (mmHg)	0.111	0.360	0.010*
DBP (mmHg)	0.282	0.544	0.000*
FPG (mmol/L)	0.142	0.399	0.004*
HOMA	0.177	0.440	0.001*
HBA1C (%)	0.370	0.619	0.000*
sCRP (mg/L)	0.733	0.859	0.000*
RF (IU/ml)	0.201	0.466	0.001*
IL-6 (pg/ml)	0.535	0.738	0.000*

Discussion

Menopause is a critical phase in a woman's life, often accompanied by significant metabolic and cardiovascular changes. Our study found that postmenopausal women had significantly higher glycemic indices, inflammatory markers, blood pressure, and total cholesterol levels compared to their premenopausal counterparts. These results align with previous research, though variations exist due to differences in population characteristics, lifestyle factors, and healthcare access.^{3,11}

The increase in fasting plasma glucose (FPG), glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), and homeostatic model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR) observed in postmenopausal women suggests a decline in insulin sensitivity. This is consistent with findings from Sathya Bhama et al. and Sloprien et al., who reported that menopause contributes to insulin resistance and a higher risk of type 2 diabetes.^{9,2} HBA1C was significantly higher in post-menopausal women which is in line with other studies.⁶ Estrogen plays a crucial role in glucose metabolism by enhancing insulin signaling and suppressing hepatic glucose production.^{10,12} Its decline during menopause likely impairs these processes, leading to increased glyceic indices. However, some studies have reported milder changes in glucose metabolism, which may be attributed to differences in dietary habits, physical activity levels, and genetic predisposition.¹² Populations with healthier diets and higher levels of physical activity may experience less severe glyceic disruptions than those in urbanized settings with more sedentary lifestyles.

Similarly, our findings showed a significant increase in inflammatory markers, including C-reactive protein (CRP), rheumatoid factor (RF), and interleukin-6 (IL-6), among postmenopausal women. This aligns with the studies of Oluboye et al. and Ridker et al., who reported elevated CRP levels, as well as Metcalfa et al. and Fried, who observed increased IL-6 in menopausal women compared to premenopausal women.^{3 16 13 17} These findings suggest that menopause is associated with heightened systemic inflammation due to estrogen depletion. However, our results contrast with those of Razmjout et al. and Yasuri et al., who found no significant difference in inflammatory markers between the two groups.^{14 15} Estrogen is known for its anti-inflammatory properties, and its decline has been linked to increased production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (Santos et al., 2021).

The strongest associations in our study were observed with CRP (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.733$, $\beta = 0.859$, $p = 0.000$) and IL-6 (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.535$, $\beta = 0.738$, $p = 0.000$), indicating that menopause is a major contributor to systemic inflammation. This suggests that inflammation plays a central role in menopause-related metabolic dysfunction. Some studies report less pronounced inflammatory changes, possibly due to differences in body composition, overall health status, and dietary habits.¹⁵ Populations with lower obesity rates and better inflammatory regulation through diet and exercise may exhibit reduced postmenopausal inflammation compared to those with higher obesity prevalence.

In addition to glyceic and inflammatory changes, our study found that postmenopausal women had significantly higher systolic (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP), consistent with research indicating that menopause contributes to increased cardiovascular risk.^{4 18} This rise in blood pressure has been linked to aging, which reduces blood vessel elasticity, as well as increased cholesterol levels in postmenopausal women, leading to vascular stenosis. Estrogen plays a crucial role in blood pressure regulation due to its vasodilatory effects, and its decline can result in vascular stiffness and hypertension. However, the extent of blood pressure elevation may vary across populations based on genetic predisposition, salt intake, and lifestyle factors.¹⁹

The observed increase in total cholesterol levels among postmenopausal women aligns with studies highlighting menopause-related dyslipidemia. Estrogen deficiency is associated with elevated total cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) levels, increasing the risk of cardiovascular diseases. However, some studies report less pronounced lipid changes, possibly due to genetic variations, dietary habits, or the use of hormone replacement therapy.^{20 21} Women with better access to lipid-lowering medications or those following traditional diets rich in healthy fats may experience a milder lipid profile shift compared to those consuming more processed foods.

This study found that BMI and WHR are significantly higher in postmenopausal women compared to premenopausal women, consistent with findings from previous research.^{22 23}

Variations in findings across studies may also be linked to socioeconomic and healthcare disparities. Western populations, where routine metabolic health monitoring and preventive care are more accessible, tend to report lower levels of inflammation and metabolic disturbances compared to African populations, where limited healthcare access may contribute to more pronounced postmenopausal metabolic. Differences in dietary intake, physical activity, and environmental factors further influence these outcomes, highlighting the importance of context-specific interventions.

In conclusion, our study confirms that menopause is significantly associated with increased glyceic indices, systemic inflammation, elevated blood pressure, and lipid alterations, all of which elevate the risk of metabolic and cardiovascular diseases. The strongest associations were observed with CRP and IL-6, further underscoring the inflammatory nature of menopause-related changes. These findings emphasize the need for targeted interventions, particularly in resource-limited settings. Lifestyle modifications such as improved diet, regular exercise, and metabolic screening should be prioritized. Future research should investigate the combined effects of genetic predisposition, lifestyle factors, and potential therapeutic approaches to better manage menopause-induced metabolic alterations, particularly among African populations.

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